

PERSONS APPOINTED TO POSITIONS IN THE PROSECUTOR'S BODIES AND REQUIREMENTS FOR THEM

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ABSTRACT

This article describes individuals appointed to positions in the prosecutor's office and the requirements for them, the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, his powers, accountability, the District Attorney's Office, the provinces, the city prosecutors of Tashkent, and their corresponding prosecutors, districts, city prosecutors, and their corresponding prosecutors.

"I am confident that the prosecutor's office will continue to carry out their very responsible and honorable task effectively, with a deep understanding that the protection of the law is a sacred duty, such as the protection of the people and the Fatherland."

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev

The changes that are taking place in the country, new priorities for socio-economic development, and the responsibilities of upholding the rule of law and strengthening the law prohibit the need to further improve the system of preparing, rehabilitating, and improving the standards of prosecutors.

In the intervening period, a comprehensive analysis of the state of law enforcement, taking measures to address the causes and conditions of violations in a timely manner, ensuring the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, and teaching the necessary knowledge and skills to support business entities have been developed.

To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared.

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Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. It is determined by such qualities as his personality, his reputation, and his desire to set an example for his relatives, children, and neighbors.

To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. The main focus should be on fundamentally changing the responsibility of employees for their work, increasing personal accountability, and achieving the formation of their work as masters.

The Office of the Attorney-General of The Republic of Uzbekistan is headed by the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who is appointed and dismissed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the first deputy, deputies, who are appointed and removed from office by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the appointment and dismissal of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan are approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan establishes chief departments, departments, and departments.

Senior aides and aides to the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, heads of departments, their deputies, senior prosecutors, prosecutors, senior investigators in individual important cases, and investigators in individual important cases are appointed to the post by the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and removed from office.

The Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan directs the prosecutor's office and oversees their activities.

Attorney General of The Republic of Uzbekistan:

- ✓ appeal to the Legislative Council of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on legislative initiative;
- ✓ may participate in the meetings of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, introduce issues for its consideration and comment on the issue being raised
- ✓ Participates in the plenary sessions of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, discusses the issues being discussed, makes proposals on explaining the Plenum on issues related to the application of the law;
- ✓ submits proposals to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on confirmation of the composition of the life of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- ✓ provides high-level titles (military titles) to employees of the prosecutor's office and appeals to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a submission to grant high-level titles (military titles);
- ✓ presents employees of the prosecutor's office to the state awards of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- ✓ awards the employees of the prosecutor's office with the breastplate "Honorary Officer of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan";

- ✓ issues orders and approves regulations on the structural divisions of prosecutors' bodies;
- ✓ makes cooperation agreements with relevant bodies of foreign countries;
- ✓ exercises other powers in accordance with the law.

Orders and other documents of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan (excluding documents of individual nature) are revoked in accordance with the decision of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if they violate the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan is accountable to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Senate of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

To the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan said:

- ❖ about legality and the state of the fight against crime — regularly;
- ❖ about serious crimes and emergencies — immediately;
- ❖ prosecutors provide information every six months about what they have done.

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While the documents of state administration and governors seriously undermine the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, the Attorney General may submit proposals to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on whether to suspend or revoke these documents.

The Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan regularly reports on his activities to the Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

The district attorney's office is headed by the District Attorney's Office, who, in conjunction with the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is appointed to his post by the District Council of Jehovah's Witnesses and discharged from his post.

The district attorney is accountable to the District Council of Jehovah's Witnesses and the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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The district attorney will be the first deputy and deputy attorney general of the Republic of Uzbekistan to be appointed and removed from office.

Departments and departments are established in the district attorney's office.

Heads of departments and departments and their deputies, senior assistant prosecutors, are appointed to the post by the District Attorney General with the approval of the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and removed from office.

Aides to the District Attorney, senior prosecutors and prosecutors from departments and departments, prosecutors-criminals, senior investigators in individual important cases and investigators, senior investigators and investigators in individual important cases are appointed to the post by the District Attorney and removed from the post.

Provinces, city prosecutors in Tashkent and their equivalent prosecutors

Prosecutors from the provinces, the city prosecutors of Tashkent, and the U.S. Transportation Prosecutor's Office are headed. The Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan is headed by the Military Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who is the deputy attorney general of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These prosecutors are subject to the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and are accountable to him.

The provinces, the city prosecutors of Tashkent, the Transport Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan are appointed to the post by the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and discharged from their posts. The Military Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan is appointed to the post by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and discharged from his post, as prescribed by the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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He will be the first deputy and deputy military prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Transport Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the provinces, and the city prosecutors of Tashkent to be appointed to the post by the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and removed from office.

Departments and departments are established in the provinces, the city prosecutor's offices of Tashkent, and their corresponding prosecutors.

The heads of departments and departments, senior assistant prosecutors, are appointed to the post by the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and removed from office.

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Districts, cities, and their equivalent prosecutors

Districts, cities, and prosecutors belonging to their corresponding prosecutors are appointed to the post by the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and removed from office. These prosecutors are subject to and are accountable to the high-ranking relevant prosecutor and the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Until districts, cities prosecutors, and their corresponding prosecutors are touched in consultation with the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, they may have deputies appointed and dismissed by the Military Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the U.S. Transportation Prosecutor, the District Attorney, the district and city prosecutors of Tashkent.

Senior aides, assistants, senior prosecutors and investigators of districts, cities and their corresponding prosecutors, senior prosecutors and investigators of the prosecutor's office, are appointed to the post by the U.S. Military Prosecutor, the U.S. Transportation Prosecutor, the District Attorney, the district and city prosecutors of Tashkent, and are removed from their posts.

Department of Economic Crime Prevention under the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan and its local divisions

Before the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan, the Department of Economic Crime Prevention (hereinafter referred to as the Department) will be formed. To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared.

The deputy head of the department is appointed to the post by the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and discharged from his post, as prescribed by the head of the department.

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The procedure, and variations of it, came to be called in vitro (in glass) fertilization, or IVF.

The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) and its regional divisions under the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan

Before the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan, the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (hereinafter referred to as the Bureau) is established. To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared.

As director of the bureau, he is the Chief Public Officer of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Vice-Presidents of the Bureau are appointed to the post by the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan and discharged from their posts, as prescribed by the Director of the Bureau.

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The heads of the district (city) departments of the bureau are appointed to the post by the Director of the Bureau and removed from their posts.

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The jury of the prosecutor's office

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Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. hear reports from prosecutors, heads of structural divisions of prosecutors, prosecutors, and other employees.

Based on life decisions, relevant prosecutors can issue injunctions.

The requirements for appointing prosecutors to the post are set out in Article 43 of the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the following are the requirements for those appointed to positions in the prosecutor's office:

- has a higher legal education;
- who had the necessary professional qualities;
- citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are appointed to provide health care to perform the duties of the service entrusted to them.

In individual cases, specialists with the necessary knowledge and experience in the field of economics, finance, sociology, information and communication technologies and other fields may be accepted for service in the prosecutor's office.

Persons under the age of twenty-five are appointed to the post of Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, The Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Prosecutor of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the District Attorney, the prosecutors of the provinces and the city of Tashkent, as well as district, city prosecutors, and their equivalent prosecutors.

Employees of the prosecutor's office must be attested in accordance with the procedure laid down by the Office of the Attorney-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Prosecutors are prohibited from engaging in other types of paid activities in addition to scientific, pedagogical and creative activities.

The swearing-in of prosecutors and investigators

The person who is being appointed to the post of prosecutor or investigator for the first time takes the following oath:

"I take a solemn oath to carry out my duties honestly and conscientiously, to fight unscrupulously against violations of the law, and to protect the interests of citizens, society, and the state."

The procedure for taking the oath is determined by the Attorney General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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1. <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/6961> ;
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On prosecution". Tashkent sh, August 29, 2001, 257-II. <https://lex.uz/docs/106197>